

Differences in organizational factors by lean duration

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Abstract The aim of this paper is to explore whether employees' perceptions towards perceived organisational support and participative decision-making vary by lean duration (i.e., the duration of lean production in operation), and whether managers' perceptions towards propensity for participative decision-making vary by the lean duration. For the study, quantitative research methodology was used and data was collected from 616 shop-floor employees and 129 middle level managers engaged full-time in export-apparel manufacturing firms that have implemented lean production systems in Sri Lanka. It was found that participative decision-making and propensity for participative decision-making significantly differ by the duration of lean production in operation.

Key words: *lean production, participative decision-making, perceived organisational support, propensity for participative decision-making.*

JEL classification: O15 - Human Resources

1 Introduction

Organisations world-wide must compete in open and global markets where survival and success depend to a large extent on distinctive internal capabilities (González-Benito, 2005). To survive and gain competitive advantage in this ever expanding and competitive global marketplace, firms have to provide quality products and services demanded by customers, delivered faster and at a lower price, through high levels of performance and commitment (Gollan, 2005). In the circumstances, lean production has gained widespread attention both in the literature and practice for its possibility to increase the efficiency of production systems and competitiveness in local as well as international markets (Bendell 2005; Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995). The implementation of lean production systems has become a common event in the business world (Bendell 2005; Zhang et al. 2006), and many organisations have found that lean production provided added benefits to stay in business and to gain competitive advantage internationally (Browning and Heath 2009; Cua et al. 2001).

The reorganisation of manufacturing processes according to the lean production requirements trigger techno-organisational changes with a new

strategy, structure, and the social organisation of work systems (Dahlgaard and Dahlgaard-Park 2006, Forza 1996, Smeds 1994). For instance, lean production demands team-based work organisation where shop-floor employees having willingness, ability and sufficient authority to participate in decision-making as well as their superiors having willingness to share decision making with shop-floor employees (Fullerton and Wempe 2009). Therefore, when capturing and capitalising on individual capabilities in the lean production, there is a need to better understand both shop-floor employees' and managers' perceptions towards employee participation.

The operations management literature suggests that variations could be found in various aspects of the human dimension based on the level of lean production implementation or for how long the lean production system is in operation (e.g., Browning and Heath 2009, Conti et al. 2006, Sohal and Egglestone 1994). However, our review of the operations management literature has shown that this information has so far not received the due attention in evaluating issues surrounding the human dimension. For instance, lean production demands a high level of employee participation. However it is difficult to create a participative work environment overnight and may need considerable time to receive acceptance from both shop-floor employees and their managers. Therefore, in this paper we propose that for how long the lean production is in operation (termed as "lean duration" in this study) will differentiate shop-floor employees' perceived organisational support (POS) and participative decision-making (PDM), and managers' propensity for participative decision-making (PPDM). In other words, we propose that the longer the lean duration is the higher will be employees' perceived POS and PDM, and managers' PPDM.

The novelty of the current study lies in the following aspects. First, the literature identifies lean production as a major theme of operations management for further inquiry and understanding (Pilkington and Fitzgerald 2006). Although the operations management literature devotes some space to highlight the importance of the human dimension in lean production or in advanced manufacturing technologies, those are mainly focused on technical aspects (see Brown and Mitchell 1991, Dahlgaard and Dahlgaard-Park 2006, Harrison and Storey 1996, McLachlin 1997). Second, the adoption of advanced manufacturing systems induces firms to increase their use of non-financial manufacturing

performance measures (see Abdel-Maksoud et al. 2005, Banker et al. 1993, Shah and Ward 2007), and previous research found that the increased utilisation of non-financial measures is strongly associated with improved organisational performance (e.g., Fullerton and Wempe 2009). In this regard, the organisational behaviour literature identifies employee work attitudes as one of such non-financial performance measures (Foong and Yorston 2003). Third, in connection with the above, our review of literature has shown that employee beliefs and attitudes to various dimensions of new manufacturing management initiatives have so far gone largely unrecorded. Our review of journals that are outlets for operations management related research in popular databases of Business Source Premier, ABI/Inform, Emerald, ScienceDirect, Springer, and Wiley Blackwell has not been able to find studies that are specifically conducted on POS, PDM or PPDM in the context of lean production. Therefore, there is no consensus regarding the extent to which, and ways in which, the adoption of lean production has implications for human resources. Hence, an exploration of these variables in the context of lean production would be able to provide an understanding of both shop-floor employees' and managers' perceptions towards employee participation.

In the above context, this study was conducted to explore 1) whether employees' perceptions towards POS and PDM vary by lean duration, and 2) whether managers' perceptions towards PPDM vary by the lean duration. For the study, quantitative research methodology was used and data was collected from 616 shop-floor employees and 129 middle level managers engaged full-time in export-apparel manufacturing firms that have implemented lean production systems in Sri Lanka. Consistent with the objectives, the next section briefly describes the Sri Lankan context related to the study and reviews the theoretical background of the study. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Thereafter, the main findings are presented and discussed. The article concludes with a discussion on the implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

2 Background of the study: Sri Lankan context

The export-apparel manufacturing industry is the leading manufacturing industry in Sri Lanka that has emerged as the country's main export earner and the largest

single employment provider in the industrial sector (Department of Census and Statistics n.d). The USA and EU have been Sri Lanka's main apparel importers accounting for over 90 percent of total Sri Lankan apparel exports. When producing apparel for developed countries in the West, local manufactures have to strictly adhere to product design specifications provided by foreign buyers who define product design and quality.

The growth witnessed by this industry can be attributed to two major factors. First, the market-oriented liberal economic policies introduced in 1977 (Fonseka and Fonseka 1998). Second, the Multi-Fibre Agreement (MFA), the worldwide system of managed trade in textiles and apparel that came into existence in 1974 (which subsequently integrated into the World Trade Organisation framework by 2005). The MFA introduced a quota system for the export of apparel products to developed countries by limiting the quantity of garments that can be exported by the developing countries to any single developed country. Therefore, the quota holding apparel exporting developing countries had been ensured a guaranteed market.

Due to rising wages and quota restrictions by MFA on East Asian economies (such as Hong Kong, South Korea and Taiwan, who were the leaders in apparel export by the late 1970s), export-apparel production shifted to quota holding Asian countries, such as Sri Lanka, Thailand, Philippines, Indonesia, China, India, and Pakistan in the late 1970s. Thereafter, the export-apparel production has, further shifted to other quota holding countries with relatively lower labour cost in Asia (such as Laos, Cambodia, Bangladesh, and Vietnam), Latin and Central America, Caribbean, Eastern Europe, and North Africa (Fonseka and Fonseka 1998, p. 255). Overall, under the quota regime, Sri Lanka like other apparel exporting developing countries had enjoyed a relatively assured export market through bilateral agreements with the developed world.

However, changes occurred when this system of managed trade perpetrated by MFA came to an end. The World Trade Organisation (WTO), which replaced the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) ushered a restriction-free world trade, set out a time period of 10 years from 1995 to 2005 for the phase-out of the MFA quota system and the integration of textiles and apparel export trade into the WTO framework. The export-apparel manufacturing industry in Sri Lanka faced this imminent phase-out of MFA quota system for the

EU by late 1990s and for the USA (and other Western countries) in 2005. In real terms phasing out of the quota system challenged the very foundation on which this industry was built. Since the phase-out of the quota system by 2005, apparel exporting countries from Asia, Latin and Central America, Caribbean, Eastern Europe, and North Africa have been competing intensively with each other for their market share. Since then, other competitive dimensions such as productivity and quality, therefore, come on centre stage. This change of priorities has influenced the rethinking of operations management strategies adopted in this sector.

Since the mid 2000s, export-apparel manufacturers in Sri Lanka identified possibilities for them to turn to lean production for improving the efficiency of their production systems. Scholars also suggest that rapid change industries adopt lean production as a growth paradigm (e.g., Duguay et al. 1997, Kojima and Kaplinsky 2004). The attributes of lean production (see Womack et al. 1990, James-Moore and Gibbons 1997, Hines et al. 2004), such as integrated, single piece production flow, low inventory, and close integration from raw material to customer through partnership fit with the high-volume repetitive export-apparel manufacturing environment in Sri Lanka. Preliminary investigations made by us revealed that export-apparel manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka are changing their production methods and management practices to become leaner and fitter to suit the new production model.

When considering the shop-floor workforce of this industry, workforce statistics (Department of Census and Statistics, n.d, Tertiary and Vocational Education Commission 2000) report that a majority of shop-floor employees are female, single, less than 25 years of age, and have secondary education less than or equal to 10 years of full-time education. Further, employees belonging to any category of the workforce of this industry are not unionised. However, it should be noted that State interventions to protect the interests of the workers who do not have equal bargaining power with the employers have resulted in the enactment of a large number of labour statutes, where some argue that the Sri Lankan labour legislation is over protective of employees and weigh heavily in favour of them (Sarveswaran n.d.). The platform indeed for the industry is better educated and trained employees; employers expect them to stay longer in a job. However, the industry experiences a monthly average turnover rate of 8% for shop-floor

employees. Therefore, when capturing and capitalising on individual capabilities, there is a need to better understand work related attitudes of employees. Further, being in the export-apparel manufacturing industry for more than 30 years, the findings of this study will provide valuable information to both academics and practitioners as it is scarce to find empirical evidence on the human dimension in lean production.

3 Theoretical background and propositions

3.1 Lean production

Bendell (2005) summarized the lean concept as “the systematic pursuit of perfect value through the elimination of waste in all aspects of the organization’s business processes. It requires a very clear focus on the value element of all products and services and a thorough understanding of the detailed operations of the business processes by which the product or service is provided (the ‘value stream’)” (p. 972). According to Womack et al. (1990) lean production is lean because it uses less of everything compared with mass production – half the human effort in the factory, half the manufacturing space, half the investment in tools, and half the engineering hours to develop a new product in half the time. Also it requires keeping far less than half the needed inventory on site, results in much fewer defects, and produces a greater and ever-growing variety of products (as cited in Sohal and Egglestone, 1994, p. 36). The literature suggests that the concept of lean production has gained widespread attention as a dominant strategy for organizing production systems (Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995).

Organisations adopt lean production as a bundle of associated practices, such as total quality management, just-in-time, continuous improvement, quality circles, and total productive maintenance (see Bonavia and Marin 2006, Browning and Heath 2009, Cua et al. 2001, González-Benito, 2005, Katayama and Bennett 1996, Shah and Ward 2003, Slack 2005; Sohal and Egglestone 1994, Zhang et al. 2006). Some authors claim that the benefits from introducing lean production are much greater if advantage is taken of synergies between different lean production practices (e.g., Cua et al. 2001, Fullerton and McWatters 2001, Pont et al. 2008, Shah and Ward 2003, Santos 2000).

Work systems conducive to lean production involves several core characteristics, such as a multi-skilled workforce taking a high degree of

responsibility for work within their areas, the interaction of groups of individuals from parallel structures in the formal organisation with a requisite variety in knowledge and capabilities, and active shop-floor problem-solving structures that are central to *kaizen* (Forza, 1996; Fullerton and Wempe, 2009; Gonzalez-Benito, 2005). These characteristics demand employee participation in decision making (PDM) to be an integral aspect of a successful lean production process (Co et al., 1998; Conti et al., 2006; Fullerton and Wempe, 2009). Further, some scholars (e.g., Co et al., 1998) argue that the human factor alone can differentiate firms who are successful in the adoption from those that are not so successful.

3.2 Lean duration

The literature on operations management suggests that variations could be found in different dimensions based on how long the lean production is in operation (Conti et al. 2006, Sohal and Egglestone 1994). For instance, in evaluating the relationship between the level of lean implementation and employees' stress levels, Conti et al. (2006) highlighted the importance of collecting and analyzing data on the degree of lean implementation at different production sites. They further claimed that the level of implementation appears to be a reasonable surrogate for how long the lean production is in operation. Further, when investigating the extent to which the lean production has been implemented and what are the structural changes taking place as a result of the implementation of lean production within Australian organisations, Sohal and Egglestone (1994) highlighted the importance of collecting data on how long the lean production system is in operation at each firm. In a similar vein, Pirraglia et al. (2009) highlighted the importance of distinguishing firms that have implemented lean production and firms that are planning to implement, etc in studying lean production systems in the United States wood industry. In this regard, Browning and Heath (2009) identified the lack of empirical attention given to contextual factors' (such as lean duration) relationship with lean practices and they have emphasized the need of analyzing the influence of contextual factors in studying lean implementations. However, we have not found studies that investigated the influence of lean duration in evaluating various aspects of the human dimension in the lean production.

However, the literature on organisational behaviour suggests that the implementation and establishment of new routines, behavioural patterns and fundamental changes in organisation culture do not happen overnight. In this regard, the operations management literature emphasises the need of substantial changes to the social organisation of work to build an environment conducive to lean production (Dahlgaard and Dahlgaard-Park 2006). The implementation of lean production systems requires organisations to adapt to new routines, new methods of work performance, behavioural patterns, and changes in organisation culture. Therefore, it could be assumed that the smooth operation of lean production necessitates fundamental rethinking and cultural changes in habits, routines and actions of both shop-floor employees and managers. In this context, we propose that when investigating human aspects in lean production, the lean duration (or for how long lean production is in operation) is an important variable. Because, to build an organisational environment that is conducive to the lean production requires a higher level of employee participation in decision making, and such environments naturally demand changes to the social organisation, which requires some time to receive acceptance from both shop-floor employees and managers. Further, we propose that longer the lean duration, the higher will be employees' POS and PDM, and managers' PPDM.

In developing an account of POS, PDM and PPDM in the following sections, an attempt will be made to establish a basis for the hypotheses that there will be significant differences in POS, PDM and PPDM by the lean duration, and those will be high in firms with a longer lean duration.

3.3 Perceived organisational support

Perceived organisational support captures an employee's beliefs concerning the extent to which the organisation values [employees'] general contributions made on the organisation's behalf and cares for their well-being (Eisenberger et al. 1986, p. 501, Eisenberger et al. 2002, p. 566). In other words, POS describes an employer's side of the exchange as perceived by employees. Therefore, an employee's beliefs of how an organisation values him or her is vital for determining whether any attitudes or behaviours benefiting the organisation emerge from the exchange relationship that takes place between the employee and the employer (Eisenberger et al. 1986, Shanock and Eisenberger 2006).

It has been argued that POS is affected by fair allocation of job rewards for the effort employees put in to meet organisational goals, which signify a belief that the organisation values the contributions of its employees (Rhoades and Eisenberger 2002). Job rewards include tangible incentives, such as pay and fringe benefits and socio-emotional benefits such as esteem, supportive and helpful supervision, approval, and caring (Eisenberger et al. 1986). Further, employees value job rewards to be based on the discretion of the organisation rather than influenced by external forces, such as unions or health and safety regulations (Dawley et al. 2008). These voluntary job rewards that come directly from the organisation are perceived as an indication that the organisation values employees' contributions made on the organisation's behalf and cares for their well-being (Dawley et al. 2008).

In the lean production setting, employees have little alternative choice instead of participating in substantive job related decision-making and problem-solving. Hence, support from the organisation for employees' job related decision-making and problem-solving is an important part of the organisational milieu that concerns the commitment of the organisation to employees (refer to Eisenberger et al. 1986).

Based on the literature reviewed above, it is proposed that for how long lean production is in operation will differentiate shop-floor employees' POS.

Therefore, the following hypothesis is developed for the study:

Hypothesis 1: There will be significant differences in POS between firms with a longer lean duration and a shorter duration, where longer the lean duration, higher will be employees' POS.

3.4 Participation in decision making

Participation in decision-making refers to the sharing of decision making, which is ordinarily the prerogative or responsibility of a manager, with subordinates to achieve organisational objectives (Cotton et al. 1988, Scott-Ladd et al. 2006, Stashevsky and Elizur 2000). Participation in decision-making is generally used to obtain employees' (non-managerial) perceptions towards their involvement and influence in job related decision-making. Participation in decision-making is central to the lean production and it is higher in the lean production plants than in traditional plants (Forza 1996). In the context of lean production, eliminating

scrap and rework is a determinant of the elimination of waste, which is the responsibility of employees. The identification of defective parts is also the responsibility of employees. Employees are allowed to stop the line in the event that defective parts are found and the responsibility for adjusting defective parts is also delegated to employees. The commitment of each employee to continuous improvement is another key principle of lean production, which is often accomplished through implementing schemes for suggestions, quality circles, and spontaneous problem solving. The use of multifunctional teams, with multi-skilled employees decreases the number of job classifications but increases the number of tasks in the team. The integration of different functions into teams means that tasks previously performed by indirect departments are integrated into the team, increasing the work content of the teams (see de Treville and Antonakis 2006, Harrison and Storey 1996, Karlsson and Åhlström 1995, Scherrer-Rathje et al. 2009). In this regard, Dahlgaard and Dahlgaard-Park (2006) state that "...lean production requires a culture where everybody is proactively working in reducing waste and in helping each partner (internal and/or external partners). Everybody understands that his/her contribution is essential for the team in which he/she is a member and for the customer. If he/she is not there – physically as well as mentally – there is a risk that the work will not be done as efficiently as possible. The success of the system depends on everybody's participation. This requires leadership for organisational excellence" (p. 572). Overall, on the one hand, employee participation increases flexibility and reduces the vulnerability of the production system (e.g., Forza 1996). On the other hand, employee participation in solving production problems and devising process improvements, increases job control, which in turn is associated with improvements in the quality of work life (e.g., Lowin 1968, Mulder 1971).

Our review of the operations management literature suggests that little empirical research has directly addressed how employees in participatory work arrangements of lean production respond to their work and the organisation. Given the interest in society concerning the quality of work life of employees in manufacturing settings (e.g., Conti et al. 2006; Vidal 2007), PDM would appear to be a candidate for increased theoretical and empirical attention in the operations management literature. Based on the literature reviewed earlier, it is proposed that

the lean duration will differentiate shop-floor employees' PDM. Therefore, the following hypothesis is developed for the study:

Hypothesis 2: There will be significant differences in PDM between firms with a longer lean duration and a shorter duration, where longer the lean duration, higher will be employees' perceived PDM.

3.5 Propensity for participative decision-making

Propensity for participative decision-making refers to the predisposition of a manager to employ PDM techniques within the organisation (Parnell and Crandall 2003, p. 49). Therefore, PPDM shows a manager's proclivity of propensity to solicit employee participation in decisions (Parnell, 2010). Evidence suggests that the success or failure of PDM may be linked to the likelihood that managers will embrace the approach (Cotton et al. 1988). In other words, managers' level of PPDM consequently impacts the level of effectiveness attained from efforts to foster employee PDM (Parnell and Crandall 2003). Parnell and Crandall (2001) suggest that PPDM is a function of four core factors, namely, individual manager's beliefs concerning the effectiveness of employee participation, perceptions about the effect of employee participation on the manager's power, the culture of the organisation in which the manager operates, and the presence of the individual manager's commitment to participative decision making (Parnell and Crandall 2001).

Of the four core factors, an individual manager's beliefs concerning the effectiveness of employee participation refers to a manager's belief that PDM enhances organisational effectiveness, and increases productivity and decision quality (Parnell and Bell 1994, Parnell and Crandall 2001). Parnell and Crandall (2001, 2003) suggest that managers who perceive that PDM will result in a loss of managerial power may be less likely to solicit employee participation. The culture of the organisation in which the manager operates refers to whether propensity for participative management is affected by the degree to which such behaviour is encouraged or discouraged by the culture of the organisation (Parnell and Crandall 2001). Finally, a manager's commitment to participative decision making is critical for the effective implementation of employee participation programmes (Parnell and Crandall 2001).

Further, Parnell and Crandall (2001, 2003) stressed the equal importance of all the four components of PPDM for success. For instance, Parnell and Crandall (2003) said that a manager's PPDM is very high when he or she believes that employee participation enhances organisational effectiveness and will not result in a decline in his or her organisational power. In a comparative study involving Mexican and Peruvian managers, Parnell (2010) identified two important situations. First, Mexican managers who believed that PDM reduces a manager's power base were also likely as others to see a positive link between PDM and organisational effectiveness. In contrast, Peruvian managers who believed that PDM reduces a manager's power base were less likely than others to see a positive link between PDM and organisational effectiveness. Second, Mexican managers operating in participative organisational cultures were less committed than other managers to participation as a management philosophy and to their organisations. In contrast, Peruvian managers operating in participative organisational cultures were more committed than other managers to participation and to their organisations (p. 2323). Such examples also justify the need of evaluating PPDM in terms of four components and in different country contexts.

Overall, Parnell and Crandall (2001, p. 531) concluded "PPDM can shed light on which aspects of the organisation are troublesome in hindering intervention strategies. Problems could be found in the areas of culture, decision ineffectiveness, individual commitment, or the feeling of perceived loss of power on the part of the manager". However, to date, the operations management literature has not adequately addressed managers' PPDM in the context of lean production. Based on the literature reviewed earlier, it is proposed that the lean duration will differentiate managers' PPDM. Therefore, the following hypothesis is developed for the study:

Hypothesis 3: There will be significant differences in PPDM between firms with a longer lean duration and a shorter duration, where longer the lean duration, higher will be managers' perceived PPDM.

Further, based on the literature reviewed above, we propose the following four hypotheses for each core dimension of PPDM.

Hypothesis 3a: There will be significant differences in managers' perception "PDM enhances organisational effectiveness" between firms with a

longer lean duration and a shorter duration, where longer the lean duration, higher will be managers' perception "PDM enhances organisational effectiveness".

Hypothesis 3b: There will be significant differences in managers' perception "participative management is affected by the degree to which such behaviour is encouraged by the culture of the organisation" between firms with a longer lean duration and a shorter duration, where longer the lean duration, higher will be managers' perception "participative management is affected by the degree to which such behaviour is encouraged by the culture of the organisation".

Hypothesis 3c: There will be significant differences in managers' perception "employee participation will not result in a decline in his or her organisational power" between firms with a longer lean duration and a shorter duration, where longer the lean duration, higher will be managers' perception "employee participation will not result in a decline in his or her organisational power".

Hypothesis 3d: There will be significant differences in managers' perception "presence of the individual manager's commitment to participative decision making is critical for the effective implementation of employee participation programmes" between firms with a longer lean duration and a shorter duration, where longer the lean duration, higher will be managers' perception "presence of the individual manager's commitment to participative decision making is critical for the effective implementation of employee participation programmes".

4 Methodology

4.1 Sample

The target population for the study is a cross section of shop-floor employees engaged full-time in export-apparel manufacturing firms, which implemented a formal lean production system in the whole manufacturing function and the lean production has become the standard of operation for at least one year in Sri Lanka. The following sample selection criteria were set for the study: 1) a firm should be registered under the Board of Investment of Sri Lanka (BOI) as it is the primary government authority responsible for identifying, promoting and facilitating both foreign and local investments in the country and export-apparel manufacturing is the major industrial category under BOI. Further, it is compulsory by BOI Act (No.4 of 1978) that all BOI registered firms should export at least 90 percent of their output. Thus, all export-apparel manufacturing firms that come under this study population are homogeneous in nature in terms of business operations; and 2) a firm should have implemented a formal lean production system in the whole manufacturing function (not as a pilot project) and that should be the standard of operation for at least one year. This criterion was set as past researchers (e.g., Pirraglia et al. 2009) suggested the importance of distinguishing firms that have implemented the lean production and firms that are planning to implement, etc. Although there are nearly 800 firms engaged in the export-apparel manufacturing industry in Sri Lanka, only 12 export-apparel manufacturing firms had fully implemented lean production systems and running for at least one year. These 12 firms were considered as the population frame for the study and all the firms agreed to participate in the survey. To fulfil the expectations of the study, it was decided to collect data from shop-floor employees and middle level managers.

A self-administered survey questionnaire was chosen as the mode for data collection. Two questionnaires were developed for the study. As discussed in the section 3.3, POS captures an employee's beliefs concerning the extent to which the organisation values their general contributions on organisation's behalf and cares for their well-being. Similarly, as discussed in the section 3.4, PDM captures employees' (non-managerial) perceptions towards their involvement and influence in job related decision-making that typically falls within the domain of the manager. Hence, shop-floor employees' questionnaire consisted of questions

relating to POS and PDM. As discussed in the section 3.5, PPDM refers to the predisposition of a manager to employ PDM techniques within the organisation (Parnell and Crandall 2003, p. 49). Hence, the managers' questionnaire consisted of questions relating to PPDM.

To ease the data collection, twelve contact persons were identified from each firm. The contact person from each firm together with one of the authors of this paper randomly selected shop-floor employees to participate in the study. In doing so, attempts were made to select a cross-section of shop-floor employees from each firm. Further, participants were briefed about the aims of the study prior to the questionnaire distribution and their responses were anonymous. One thousand survey questionnaires were distributed among the firms covering at least 5% of the total shop-floor employees in each firm. 616 usable responses resulted in a 62% response rate. With regard to the managers' sample, the number of middle level managers attached to the production function in this industry compared to shop-floor employees is very limited. The ratio between shop-floor employees and middle level managers was about 30:1. Two hundred survey questionnaires were distributed among the firms covering at least 10% of the total middle level managers attached to the production function in each firm. A total of 129 usable responses resulted in a 65% response rate.

With regard to the characteristics of the responding firms, the oldest firm was established in the year 1993 while the youngest firm was established in the year 2004. All the firms have adopted lean production methods after 2005, where the latest adoption occurred in two of the firms in the year 2007. When the firm size is measured in terms of average annual turnover in US\$ and the number of people employed, the respondent firms had an average annual turnover (in US\$) ranging from 50 to 250 Million while the total number of employees ranged from 300 to 5000. All the firms had a dedicated section to handle lean implementation headed by a senior level manager. Although we wanted to gather secondary data on the intensity of lean implementation the firms were reluctant to provide such data. The demographics of the samples are shown in Table I.

Take in Table 1

4.2 Measures

Variables of POS, PDM and PPDM were measured using a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). In this regard, Kulas et al. (2008) found that a middle response category did not adversely affect reliability and validity in social research. For all measurement scales, standardised Cronbach's alpha was examined and principal components factor analysis (Varimax rotation) was conducted. The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.5 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7 (see Hair et al 2006). The items of each factor were averaged to produce a mean score for the each construct.

Perceived organisational support was measured using the eight-item short version of Eisenberger et al.'s (1997) POS scale. The standardised estimates and reliability statistics for this factor are provided in Appendix 1.

Participation in decision making was measured by three items adapted from White and Ruh (1973). This scale was also used by Stashevsky and Elizur (2000) to analyse the effect of PDM on quality management. The standardised estimates and reliability statistics for this factor are provided in Appendix 2.

Propensity for participative decision-making was measured using the 18-item Parnell and Crandall's (2001) PPDM scale. The 18-item measure had a reliability of 0.776. Factor analysis yielded a set of four factors, which explained 67 percent of the variance. Each factor comprised of the same PPDM dimensions identified by Parnell and Crandall (2001). Therefore, Factor 1 was labelled as "Decision effectiveness", Factor 2 as "Organisational culture", Factor 3 as "Power", and Factor 4 as "Commitment". The standardised estimates and reliability statistics for these factors are provided in Appendix 3.

4.3. Data analysis procedure

Multivariate analysis of variance was conducted to check whether any group differences exist among the responses from the 12 firms for the three latent variables of the study. The results of the Wilks' Lambda statistics for the three

variables revealed that significant differences do not exist ($p > 0.05$) among the responses from the 12 firms.

The study relied on self-reported data. In this regard, Spector (1994) suggests that cross-sectional self-report methodology can be quite useful in providing a picture of and inter-correlations among people's job environment and their reactions to jobs, which can be useful for deriving hypotheses about how people react to jobs. However, when self-report measures from a single source are used to evaluate variables, the literature identifies several issues related to cross-sectional self-report methodology (Guest, 2001; Podsakoff et al., 2003). For instance, Guest (2001, p. 1100) states that "it is particularly difficult to obtain outcome measures. The popular solution is to use subjective indicators which, superficially at least, might overcome the problem of comparison across sectors. However there are central problems: positive response bias, the use of general single-item measures, and the level of information about the outcomes possessed by the respondent". To overcome the first problem, factor analysis was used following recommended guidelines by Hair et al. (2006). In the current study, to measure a particular variable, multiple item measures that have demonstrated good reliability and validity in previous studies were used and attempted to overcome the second problem. To overcome the third problem, as suggested by Guest (2001) more than one respondent was used. Further, the anonymity of the respondents was ensured to reduce evaluation apprehension (a procedure recommended by Podsakoff et al., 2003).

Data on the lean duration were measured in years. Our preliminary investigations in the Sri Lankan apparel industry led to identify that at least two and half years are required for a firm to create a sustainable lean production system. Further, it should be noted that one of our sample selection criteria was that a firm should have implemented a formal lean production system in the whole manufacturing function (not as a pilot project) and that it should be the standard of operation for at least one year (refer to section 4.1). Therefore, to make data feasible for independent sample t-test and logistic regression, we have recoded these into a dummy variable (0 = 1 to 2.5 years; 1 = more than 2.5. years).

With regard to the methods of data analysis, as detailed in section 4.1, data relating to POS and PDM were collected from shop-floor employees ($N = 616$) while data related to PPDM were collected from middle level managers ($N =$

129). Therefore, these two data sets were analysed separately. The main methods of data analysis were descriptive statistics, independent sample t-test, and logistic regression.

We controlled two organisation characteristics (i.e., firm size in terms of the number of employees and firms' age in terms of the years of industry presence) and five individual demographic characteristics (i.e., gender, marital status, education, age, and firm tenure) in the analysis. Respondents' gender (male - 0, female - 1), marital status (single - 0, married - 1) and the highest level of education (less than or equal to O/L - 0, up to A/L - 1) were binary coded. Respondents' age, respondents' tenure, firms' size and firms' age were log transformed.

5 Results

Table 2 shows descriptive statistics and zero-order correlations for POS, PDM and the lean duration.

Take in Table 2

The differences in POS and PDM by the lean duration were analysed using t-test. Results are shown in Table 3. As can be seen from Table 3, POS does not vary by the lean duration. This does not support the first hypothesis. However, PDM significantly vary by the lean duration ($p < .001$), where PDM is higher when the lean duration is more than 2.5 years. Hence, the second hypothesis is supported by the data.

Take in Table 3

The results of the logistic regression for POS and PDM are shown in Table 4. Nagelkerke R^2 was 0.682 suggesting that 68% of the variance is explained by the covariates. P value of 0.632 of Hosmer and Lemeshow test suggests a good fit. The overall percentage of cases correctly classified is 77 (77.4%). It is evident from Table 4 that PDM is an important human dimension that discriminates between the lean duration of 1 to 2.5 years and more than 2.5 years. For instance, the odds of lean duration of more than 2.5 years to perceive a higher level of PDM (as opposed to lean duration of 1 to 2.5 years) are four times (4.07) as high.

Take in Table 4

Table 5 shows descriptive statistics and zero-order correlations for the four components of PPDM and the lean duration.

Take in Table 5

The differences in the four components of PPDM by the lean duration were analysed using t-test. Results are shown in Table 6. As can be seen from Table 6, organisational culture (H3b, $p < .001$) and commitment (H3d, $p < .001$) show significant differences by the lean duration, where both organisational culture and commitment are higher when the lean duration is more than 2.5 years. However, decision effectiveness (H3a) and power (H3c) do not vary by the lean duration. Hence, the third hypothesis is partially supported.

Take in Table 6

The results of the logistic regression for the four components of PPDM are shown in Table 7. Nagelkerke R^2 was 0.732 suggesting that 73% of the variance is explained by the covariates. P value of 0.824 of Hosmer and Lemeshow test suggests a good fit. The overall percentage of cases correctly classified is 78 (78.82%). It is evident from Table 7 that organisational culture (H3b) and commitment (H3d) are important human dimensions that discriminate between the lean duration of 1 to 2.5 years and more than 2.5 years. For instance, the odds of lean duration of more than 2.5 years to have more conducive organisational culture for the lean production (as opposed to lean duration of 1 to 2.5 years) are almost four times (3.67) as high. Similarly, the odds of lean duration of more than 2.5 years to have a higher level of managers' commitment for the lean production (as opposed to lean duration of 1 to 2.5 years) are three times (3.19) as high.

Take in Table 7

6 Discussion, conclusions and implications

This article explored the differential effects of POS, PDM and PPDM by the lean duration. As employees' POS and PDM and managers' PPDM are two outcomes desired by organisations - from the part of the shop-floor employees and managers in the lean production context - the findings presented in this paper would be of interest to both academics and practitioners.

In this study, we considered lean duration or the duration of lean production in operation as a contextual factor that could differentiate three human dimensions related to shop-floor employees (i.e., POS and PDM) and managers (i.e., PPDM). To fulfil the objectives of the study, data were collected from 616 shop-floor employees and 129 middle level managers employed in organisations that adopted lean production practices and belonged to one of the leading industries of Sri Lanka. We have used widely accepted multiple parameters drawn from the earlier reviewed literature to evaluate employees' POS and PDM and managers' PPDM. The item scales were shown to be valid and reliable in the Sri Lankan context.

The first hypothesis predicted that significant differences will exist in the level of POS by the lean duration, where longer the lean duration, higher will be employees' POS. However, the results of the study revealed that POS does not differ by the duration of lean production in operation (lean duration of up to 2.5 years $\bar{X} = 3.91$, lean duration of more than 2.5 years $\bar{X} = 3.94$, $p > .05$). These results imply that employees do not see any difference in the support they received from the organisation for their substantive contributions to the functioning of the lean production system by the lean duration. It may be because organisations are supporting the employees through out in the same manner irrespective of the time duration of lean production implementation. Previous research in the organisational behaviour literature also identifies the support for employees from the organisation is an important part of the organisational milieu (see Eisenberger et al. 1986). The operations management literature also suggests the importance of POS in the context of advanced manufacturing systems (e.g., Dahlgaard and Dahlgaard-Park 2006, Vidal 2007). However, we have not come across previous empirical studies that investigated POS in the operations management literature to make straight forward comparisons with our results.

The second hypothesis predicted that significant differences will exist in the level of PDM by the lean duration, where longer the lean duration, higher will be employees' perceived PDM. The findings of the study revealed that PDM significantly differs by the lean duration, where PDM is higher when the duration of lean production in operation is longer than otherwise. Therefore, the second hypothesis is supported by the data. For the smooth operation of lean production, organisations expect their employees to exhibit a higher level of PDM. In this regard, employees' understanding of the concepts behind lean production, the importance of participation, their capabilities in participatory methods, and their willingness to participate are vital for the effective operation of a lean production system (see Co et al. 1998). However, the results suggest that for employees to understand the participatory management behind the lean production system and to learn required capabilities, to increase their willingness to participate in making decisions, and ultimately for them to adjust to the system take time. Therefore, the results of the study suggest the need of identifying which aspects of the organisation are troublesome in hindering employee participation in decision

making and what management strategies are to be used to overcome such hindrances both in the short-term and long-term.

The third hypothesis predicted that significant differences will exist in the level of PPDM by the lean duration, where longer the lean duration, higher will be managers' perceived PPDM. Propensity for participative decision-making reveals managers' propensity for participative decision making. As suggested by the literature reviewed above, we tested the four component model of PPDM. The results of the factor analysis support the contention that PPDM is a function of four core components. These factors were managers' beliefs concerning the effectiveness of employee PDM, perceptions about the effect of employee PDM on managers' power, the culture of the organisation in which they operate, and the presence of managers' commitment to PDM. We developed four hypotheses (3a, 3b, 3c, and 3d) to represent each core component of PPDM. The findings supported hypotheses 3b and 3d. Therefore, the third hypothesis is partially supported by the data. The following paragraphs discuss the findings related to each core component of PPDM.

The hypothesis 3a predicted that significant differences will exist in managers' perception "PDM enhances organisational decision effectiveness" by the lean duration. However, it was found that managers' beliefs concerning the effectiveness of employee PDM, which obtained considerably higher mean values for both categories of the lean duration, do not differ by the duration of lean production in operation. This implies as suggested by Parnell and Bell (1994) and Parnell and Crandall (2001) that managers perceive organisational decision effectiveness from the beginning of the lean implementation throughout the factory floor in terms of increased productivity and decision quality. Hence, as suggested by Parnell (2010, p. 2325) managers are likely to employ participative interventions when he or she believes that such will improve organisational decision effectiveness.

The hypothesis 3b predicted that significant differences will exist in managers' perception "participative management is affected by the degree to which such behaviour is encouraged by the culture of the organisation" by the lean duration. As predicted, significant differences were found in the culture of the organisation in which managers' operate by the duration of lean production in operation, where culture is more conducive for the lean production when the

duration of lean production in operation is longer than otherwise. In this regard, Parnell (2010, p. 2326) suggests that organisational culture determines the meaning (including essence) that its members attribute to PDM, reasons for soliciting participation, who should be involved, and issues that should be resolved through participation. Therefore, the findings of our study imply that changes in the organisational culture may be quite highly affected by the lean implementation and thus, to create an organisational culture where participation encouraged and practiced will take considerable time.

The hypothesis 3c predicted that significant differences will exist in managers' perception "employee participation will not result in a decline in his or her organisational power" by the lean duration. However, the results of the study revealed that managers' perception does not differ by the duration of lean production in operation (lean duration of up to 2.5 years $X = 3.15$, lean duration of more than 2.5 years $X = 3.30$, $p > .05$). In this regard, Robbins and Coulter (2005, p. 436) identify five different types of an individual's power. That is legitimate power associated with the position in the organisation, coercive power associated with the ability to punish and control subordinates, reward power associated with ability to give positive benefits or rewards, expert power associated with expertise, special skills or knowledge, and referent power associated with a person's desirable resources or personal traits. The findings may suggest that participatory interventions do not significantly influence a manager's power associated with his or her expertise and that the managers do not become fully dependent on subordinates for expertise.

The hypothesis 3d predicted that significant differences will exist in the level of managers' perception "presence of the individual manager's commitment to participative decision making is critical for the effective implementation of employee participation programmes" by the lean duration. As predicted, significant differences were found in managers' commitment to employees' PDM, where managers' commitment is comparatively higher when the duration of the lean production in operation is longer than otherwise. Further, of the four components of PPDM, the least scored PPDM component is managers' commitment at both categories of the lean duration (lean duration of up to 2.5 years $X = 2.43$, lean duration of more than 2.5 years $X = 2.86$) compared to the other three PPDM components. Therefore, the findings of our study imply that

managers' long-term commitment to participation is critical for the effective implementation of employee involvement programmes.

With regard to the findings of the current study, it should be noted that there is surprisingly little empirical research addressing the human dimension in the operations management literature. Further, although some past research (e.g., Browning and Heath 2009, Conti et al. 2006, Sohal and Egglestone 1994) suggest that there may be differences in various dimensions of lean production by the lean duration we have not come across previous empirical research that directly addressed the variables of our study. Therefore, considerable future research is necessary to investigate the propositions we made in this study. The current study represents a step in that direction.

Overall, significant differences in employees' perceptions towards their PDM and managers' beliefs towards the culture of the organisation in which they operate and their commitment to employees' PDM have implications for practice. When participation is considered as a part of the organisational culture (see Zamanou and Glaser 1994), comparatively longer time duration is needed to make the necessary cultural shifts in building an environment conducive for the lean production. Further, employees' PDM also becomes higher when the duration of the lean production in operation is long. Therefore, the state of the organisational culture may influence both managers' as well as employees' tendency to adapt to participative management techniques. This tendency is consistent with the findings of previous research, in general (see O'Connor 1995, Zamanou and Glaser 1994). Hence, organisations should take steps to identify areas of culture that are troublesome in hindering lean production in the short-term as well as in the long-term to take adequate steps to insure effective implementation of lean production systems. Furthermore, effective operation of a lean production system requires enduring commitment from managers. The low mean values at the two time periods for managers' commitment imply that their commitment towards participation is not appropriate for the context of lean production compared to the mean values of other three components of PPDM. Therefore, the findings also imply that organisations have to take necessary steps to increase managers' commitment towards participative decision making. On the whole, the results of the study could shed light on the organisational environment of the lean

production and its differences by the duration of lean production in operation from both shop-floor employees' and managers' perception.

7 Limitations and directions for future research

First, this research focused on a limited number of variables related to the human dimension in lean production. Second, the study relied on self-reported data. However, as stated in the section on the *data analysis procedure*, attempts were made to overcome issues related to self-report data. Third, we faced difficulties in collecting secondary data relating to the intensity of lean production from firms that participated in the survey. Further, there is no central data-base in Sri Lanka for us to obtain data from non-lean firms for comparison. Fourth, we explored the differences using t-test. Therefore, the interrelationship between employees' POS and PDM is beyond the focus of this study and has not been explored as a result. Finally, the study was confined to the export-apparel industry as lean practices are not yet well established in the other industrial and service sectors compared to the export-apparel industry of Sri Lanka.

With regard to specific areas for future research, as outcomes resulting from cultural shifts in the lean production context are difficult to be measured from a cross sectional study, future research could be designed as longitudinal studies and could be complimented questionnaire surveys with interviews and secondary data. However, as stated by Guest (2001, p. 1103), longitudinal research presents a further distinctive set of challenges in exploring human related variables. Further, the validation of a measure requires an assessment of measurement properties over a variety of samples in similar and different contexts. Therefore, future research in different samples is necessary.

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improvement practices. *International Journal of Operations & Production
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Tables

Table 1 Demographics of the samples

Shop-floor employees (N=616)		Managers (N=129)	
Gender:		Gender:	
Male	41%	Male	77%
Female	59%	Female	23%
Marital status:		Marital status:	
Single	64%	Single	55%
Married	36%	Married	45%
Age:		Age:	
Mean	25 yrs	Mean	34 yrs
S.D.	4.84	S.D.	3.05
Tenure in the present workplace:		Tenure in the present workplace:	
Mean	4 yrs	Mean	6 yrs
S.D.	2.46	S.D.	3.56
Highest level of education:		Highest level of education:	
Less than or equal G.C.E.(O/L)†	67%	Diploma	45%
Up to G.C.E.(A/L)‡	33%	Degree	55%
Lean duration:		Lean duration:	
1 to 2.5 years	64%	1 to 2.5 years	43%
More than 2.5 years	36%	More than 2.5 years	57%

† General Certificate in Education (Ordinary Level), ‡ General Certificate in Education (Advanced Level)

Table 2 Correlations – POS, PDM and lean duration

	Mean	S.D.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1 Gender ^a	.30	.87	1								
2 Marital status ^a	.51	.44	.032	1							
3 Age ^b	.52	.65	.096*	.289**	1						
4 Education ^a	.41	.83	.015	.149**	.035	1					
5 Tenure ^b	.43	.28	.076	.170**	.394**	.105*	1				
6 No. of employees ^b	.69	.47	.064	.129*	.040	.018	.270**	1			
7 Industry presence ^b	.84	.32	.053	.072	.022	.049	.191**	.017	1		
8 POS	3.92	.55	.106*	.065	.046	.022	.005	.228**	.313**	1	
9 PDM	3.79	.53	.084	.045	.102*	.124*	.099*	.107*	.291**	.372**	1
10 Lean duration ^a	.56	.48	.059	.051	.006	.009	.104*	.061	.048	.025	.148**

* significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). ** significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

^a Binary-coded variables, ^b Log transformed.

Table 3 t-test results - POS and PDM

	Lean duration				<i>t</i>	<i>P</i> value
	1 to 2.5 years		More than 2.5 years			
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
POS	3.91	.60	3.94	.49	-.620	.267
PDM	3.73	.56	3.90	.45	-3.940	.000***

*** $p < .001$

Table 4 Summarised results of logistic regression – POS and PDM

	B	S.E.	Wald	Exp(B)	95.0% C.I. for EXP(B)	
					Lower	Upper
Gender	.348	.308	1.283	.706	.386	1.290
Marital status	.343	.324	1.118	.710	.376	1.340
Age	.149	.302	.245	.861	.643	1.097
Education	.950	.266	5.626	.350	.208	.589
Tenure	.845	.193	9.117	.628	.594	.399
No. of employees	.432	.319	.438	.323	.284	.595
Industry presence	.593	.183	1.152	.347	.211	.632
POS	.406	.346	1.372	.800	.761	.958
PDM	1.405***	.339	17.227	4.076	2.099	7.914
Constant	.843	.626	2.919	.003		

*** $p < .001$.

Table 5 Correlations - four components of PPDM and lean duration

	Mean	S.D.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1 Gender ^a	.30	.87	1										
2 Marital status ^a	.51	.44	.032	1									
3 Age ^b	.52	.65	.096	.289**	1								
4 Education ^a	.41	.83	.015	.149**	.035	1							
5 Tenure ^b	.43	.28	.076	.170**	.394**	.105*	1						
6 No. of employees ^b	.69	.47	.064	.129*	.040	.018	.270**	1					
7 Industry presence ^b	.84	.32	.053	.072	.022	.049	.191**	.017	1				
8 Decision effectiveness	4.22	.55	.125*	.014	.129*	.150**	.112*	.102*	.089	1			
9 Organizational culture	3.80	.61	.088	.118*	.036	.018	.076	.083	.075	.217**	1		
10 Power	3.24	.80	.055	.064	.056	.008	.112*	.231**	.102*	.146*	.255**	1	
11 Commitment	2.68	.84	.029	.025	.022	.046	.015	.117*	.157**	.077	.034	.128*	1
12 Lean duration ^a	.56	.48	.059	.051	.006	.009	.104*	.061	.048	.111*	.283**	.089	.259**

* significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). ** significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

^a Binary-coded variables, ^b Log transformed.

Table 6 t-test results - components of PPDM

	Lean duration				<i>t</i>	<i>P</i> value
	1 to 2.5 years		More than 2.5 years			
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
Decision effectiveness	4.15	.55	4.27	.54	-1.255	.106
Organizational culture	3.60	.51	3.95	.64	-3.325	.000***
Power	3.15	.72	3.30	.86	-1.002	.259
Commitment	2.43	.78	2.86	.84	-3.016	.000***

*** $p < .001$

Table 7 Summarised results of logistic regression – four components of PPDM

	B	S.E.	Wald	Exp(B)	95.0% C.I. for EXP(B)	
					Lower	Upper
Gender	.157	.590	3.842	.314	.099	1.000
Marital status	1.953	.533	.412	.650	.479	.952
Age	.581	.469	1.535	.559	.223	1.402
Education	.093	.279	.110	.741	.635	.895
Tenure	.006	.302	.012	.706	.556	.819
No. of employees	.431	.392	.584	.836	.734	.982
Industry presence	.583	.427	.719	.508	.459	.721
Decision effectiveness	.372	.462	.646	1.450	.586	3.587
Organizational culture	1.300**	.477	7.433	3.671	1.441	9.350
Power	.285	.310	.849	.752	.410	1.379
Commitment	1.161***	.321	13.072	3.194	1.702	5.994
Constant	8.140**	2.779	8.577	.320		

*** $p < .001$, ** $p < .01$.

Appendix 1 Summarised results of factor analysis –POS

	Factor loading
The organization values my contribution to its well-being	.867
The organization shows very little concern for me (R)	.834
The organization really cares about my well-being	.801
Even if I did the best job possible, the organization would fail to notice (R)	.783
The organization cares about my general satisfaction at work	.772
The organization fails to appreciate any extra effort from me (R)	.745
The organization would ignore any complaint from me (R)	.731
The organization takes pride in my accomplishments at work	.717
Explained variation	73.16%
Eigenvalue	2.895
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	.760

R= Reverse coded

Appendix 2 Summarised results of factor analysis –PDM

	Factor loading
I influence on decisions concerning my work group	.856
I propose suggestions for improvements	.832
I influence on decisions concerning my job	.796
Explained variation	75.72%
Eigenvalue	3.20
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	.881

Appendix 3 Summarised results of factor analysis –PPDM

	F1: Decision effectiveness	F2: Organizational culture	F3: Power	F4: Commitment
Participative decision making is an effective communication tool	.792			
Participative decision making stimulates feelings of self-worth for subordinates	.782			
Participative decision making promotes positive relationships at all levels of the organization	.741			
Participative decision making is an effective management style over the long term	.716			
Participative decision making usually results in effective decisions	.643			
Group decisions are worth though any extra time is required	.590			
Many organizational problems disappear when everyone has a chance to participate in decision making	.585			
Participative decision making is widely used in my organisation		.765		
Participative decision making is promoted within my organization		.634		
My subordinates tend to possess the same organisational goals that I have		.736		
My subordinates are generally informed and experienced		.759		
I am free to make decisions as I wish in my organization		.739		
My boss frequently solicits my participation in his/her decisions		.698		
Participative decision making requires divulging too much confidential information (R)			.847	
Participative decision making gives too much power to subordinates (R)			.758	
Subordinates often cannot be trusted (R)			.644	
It is better for a manager not to solicit subordinate participation than to do so and ignore the suggestions (R)				.774
Participation works in some cases, but most of the time the manager should make the decision based on his or her expertise (R)				.636
Explained variation	30.813	13.485	8.913	7.075
Eigenvalue	4.622	2.023	1.337	1.061
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	.828	.815	.745	.701

R= Reverse coded